

FDI in Retail Sector in India: Strategic Implications and Challenges

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Abstract

Indian retail industry is one of the sunrise sectors with huge growth potential. According to the Investment Commission of India, the retail sector is expected to grow almost three times its current levels to \$660 billion by 2015. However, in spite of the recent developments in retailing and its immense contribution to the economy, retailing continues to be the least evolved industries and the growth of organised retailing in India has been much slower as compared to rest of the world. Undoubtedly, this dismal situation of the retail sector, despite the ongoing wave of incessant liberalization and globalization, stems from the absence of an FDI encouraging policy in the Indian retail sector. In this context, the present paper attempts to analyse the strategic issues concerning the influx of foreign direct investment in the Indian retail industry. Moreover, with the latest move of the government to allow FDI in the multibrand retailing sector, the paper analyzes the reason why foreign retailers are interested in India, the strategies they are adopting to enter India and their prospects in India. The findings of the study point out that FDI in retail would undoubtedly enable India Inc to integrate its economy with that of the global economy. Thus, as a matter of fact FDI in the buzzing Indian retail sector should not just be freely allowed but should be significantly encouraged.

Keywords: Organised retail, sunrise sector, globalisation, foreign direct investment, strategic issues and prospects.

Introduction

The Indian retail industry is the fifth largest in the world. Comprising of organized and unorganized sectors, retail industry is one of the fastest growing industries in India, especially over the last few years. With growing market demand, the industry is expected to grow at a pace of 25-30% annually. The Indian retail industry is expected to grow from Rs. 35,000 crore in 2004-05 to Rs. 109,000 crore by the year 2010. The Indian retail industry is the most promising emerging market for investment. In 2007, the retail trade in India had a share of 8- 10% in the GDP (Gross Domestic Product) of the country. In 2009, it rose to 12%. It is also expected to reach 22% by 2010(Kearney, A.T). According to the Investment Commission of India, the retail sector is expected to grow almost three times its current levels to \$660 billion by 2015. It is expected that India will be among the top 5 retail markets then. The organized sector is expected to grow to \$100 bn and account for 12-15% of retail sales by 2015(Singhal 1999). However, in late 1990's the retail sector has witnessed a level of transformation. Though initially, the retail industry in India was mostly unorganized, however with the change of tastes and preferences of the consumers, the industry is getting more popular these days and getting organized as well. Foreign direct investment (FDI) in the retail sector in India is restricted. In 2006, the government eased retail policy for the first time, allowing up to 51 per cent FDI through the single brand retail route. Since then, there has been a steady increase in FDI in the retail sector, and the cumulative FDI in single-brand retail stood at \$195 million by the middle of 2010 (DIPP, 2010).

According to the Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion (DIPP) of the Government of India, single-brand retail comprises those retailers selling products "of a 'single brand' only, such that products should be sold under the same brand internationally; and single-brand product retailing covers only products which are branded during manufacturing. In this category, FDI is allowed to the extent of 51 per cent In contrast, no FDI is allowed in the multi-brand retail category. This includes all firms in organized retail that seek to stock and sell multiple brands, such as large international retailers like Wal-Mart and Carrefour.

Strategic Issues Concerning Retail Sector In India

Retailing is the largest private industry in India and second largest employer after agriculture. The sector contributes to around 10 percent of GDP. With over 12 million retail outlets, India has the highest retail outlets density in the world. This sector witnessed significant development in the past 10 years from small unorganized family owned retail formats to organized retailing. Liberalization of the economy, rise in per capita income and growing consumerism has encouraged large business and venture capitalist in investing in retail infrastructure. The importance of retail sector in India can be judged from following facts (a) Retail sector is the largest contributor to the Indian GDP (b) The retail sector provides 15% employment (c) India has world largest retail network with 12 million outlets (d) Total market size of retailing in India is U.S \$ 180 billion (e) Current share of organized retailing is just 2% which comes around to \$3.6 trillion (f) organized retail sector is growing @ 28% per annum. The Indian retail sector is very

different from that of the developed countries. In the developed countries, products and services normally reach consumers from the manufacturer/producers through two different channels: (a) via independent retailers ('vertical separation') and (b) directly from the producer ('vertical integration'). In the latter case, the producers establish their own chains of retail outlets, or develop franchises. On the other hand, Indian retail industry is divided into organised and unorganised sectors. Organised retailing refers to trading activities undertaken by licensed retailers, that is, those who are registered for sales tax, income tax, etc. These include the corporate-backed supermarkets and retail chains, and also the privately owned giant retail businesses. Unorganised retailing, on the other hand, refers to the traditional formats of low-cost retailing, for example, the local kirana shops, owner manned general stores, paan/beedi shops, convenience stores, hand cart and pavement vendors, etc. Unorganized retailing is by far the prevalent form of trade in India – constituting 98% of total trade, while organized trade accounts only for the remaining 2% – and this is projected to increase to 15-20 per cent by 2010. Nonetheless the organized sector is expected to grow faster than GDP growth in next few years driven by favorable demographic patterns, changing lifestyles, and strong income growth.

Growth Drivers in India for Retail Sector

The retail industry in India is currently growing at a great pace and is expected to go up to US\$ 833 billion by the year 2013. It is further expected to reach US\$ 1.3 trillion by the year 2018 at a CAGR of 10%. As the country has got a high growth rate, the consumer spending has also gone up and is also expected to go up further in the future. In the last four years, the consumer spending in India climbed up to 75%. As a result, the Indian retail industry is expected to grow further in the future days. By the year 2013, the organized sector is also expected to grow at a CAGR of 40%. The key factors that drive growth in retail industry are young demographic profile, increasing consumer aspirations, growing middle class incomes and improving demand from rural markets. Also, rising incomes and improvements in infrastructure are enlarging consumer markets and accelerating the convergence of consumer tastes. Liberalization of the Indian economy, increase in spending percapita income and the advent of dual income families also help in the growth of retail sector. Moreover, consumer preference for shopping in new environs, availability of quality real estate and mall management practices and a shift in consumer demand to foreign brands like McDonalds, Sony, Panasonic, etc. also contributes to the spiral of growth in this sector. Furthermore, the Internet revolution is making the Indian consumer more

accessible to the growing influences of domestic and foreign retail chains. Reach of satellite T.V. channels is helping in creating awareness about global products for local markets. About 47% of India's population is under the age of 20; and this will increase to 55% by 2015. This young population, which is technology-savvy, watch more than 50 TV satellite channels, and display the highest propensity to spend, will immensely contribute to the growth of the retail sector in the country. Moreover, the retail sector also acts as an important employment absorber for the present social system. Thus, when a factory shuts down rendering workers jobless; or peasants find themselves idle during part of the year or get evicted from their land; or the stagnant manufacturing sector fails to absorb the fresh entrants into the job market, the retail sector absorbs them all.

Challenges of Retailing in India

In India the retailing industry has a long way to go and to become a truly flourishing industry, retailing needs to cross various hurdles. The first challenge facing the organized retail sector is the competition from unorganized sector. Needless to say, the Indian retail sector is overwhelmingly swarmed by the unorganized retailing with the dominance of small and medium enterprises in contradiction to the presence of few giant corporate retailing outlets. The trading sector is also highly fragmented, with a large number of intermediaries who operate at a strictly local level and there is no 'barrier to entry', given the structure and scale of these operations (Singhal 1999). The tax structure in India favors small retail business. Organized retail sector has to pay huge taxes, which is negligible for small retail business. Thus, the cost of business operations is very high in India. Developed supply chain and integrated IT management is absent in retail sector. This lack of adequate infrastructure facilities, lack of trained work force and low skill level for retailing management further makes the sector quite complex. Also, the intrinsic complexity of retailing-rapid price changes, threat of product obsolescence, low margins, high cost of real estate and dissimilarity in consumer groups are the other challenges that the retail sector in India is facing. The status of the retail industry will depend mostly on external factors like Government regulations and policies and real estate prices, besides the activities of retailers and demands of the customers also show impact on retail industry. Even though economy across the globe is slowly emerging from recession, tough times lie ahead for the retail industry as consumer spending still has not seen a consistent increase. In fact, consumer spending could contract further as banks have been overcautious in lending. Thus, retailers are witnessing an uphill task in terms

of wooing consumers, despite offering big discounts. Additionally, organized retailers have been facing a difficult time in attracting customers from traditional kirana stores, especially in the food and grocery segment. In retail sector, Automatic approval is not allowed for foreign investment. There are restrictions on Foreign Direct Investment imposed in order to protect the interests of the country and also in order to allow the domestic companies to make more profits with less competition than that of in the presence of rival international firms. The retail trading in India constitutes as one of those few sectors where FDI is not freely and healthily allowed.

Strategic Implications of Fdi in Retail

In spite of the recent developments in retailing and its immense contribution to the economy, it still continues to be the least evolved industries and the growth of organised retailing in India has been much slower as compared to rest of the world. Over a period of 10 years, the share of organised retailing in total retailing has grown from 10 per cent to 40 percent in Brazil and 20 percent in China, while in India it is only 2 per cent (between 1995-2005). One important reason for this is that retailing is one of the few sectors where foreign direct investment is not allowed. Within the country, there have been protests by trading associations and other stakeholders against allowing FDI in retailing. On the other hand, the growing market has attracted foreign investors and India has been portrayed as an important investment destination for the global retail chains (<http://www.articlesbase.com>). The need for larger FDI is because India is at a stage where it needs US investments, technology, and management policies to sustain and enhance its economic growth. In 2006, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in India amounted to US\$37 billion, out of which only \$5 billion was from the US. This was not a very encouraging figure in view of the goal of increasing the GDP by 34-36%. India still requires an FDI component equal to 4% of the GDP. The US needs to invest more in various sectors of the Indian economy. As such, India is rated as the 2nd best economy to invest in, after China. India is looking forward to a high growth rate of almost 16% – double that of the current 8%. Hence, there is a distinct need for larger FDI. There are other necessities which a larger FDI will cater to viz., employment generation, income generation, technology transfer, and economic stability. Hence, the need for larger FDI is a pressing situation these days in India. Foreign countries are well aware of this, and many of them are taking extra initiative to invest in the Indian economy.

Lately there has been a remarkable surge in the demand for the liberalization of the Indian retail sector both at the domestic and as well as at the

international front and it seems that the government is giving the matter a very pensive and careful consideration. Some of the factors that have contributed to this trend are the evident profits in the ever growing but conserved Indian retails sector, reduction in tariff, cheaper real time communications, and cheaper transport. The main reasons for such an unequivocal demand stems from the realization that (i) while the retail sector requires heavy investment for expansion, there is hardly any local capital left in the capital markets as a consequence of global financial meltdown, and (ii) efficient management of multi-brand, multi-product, multi location retail, especially in the area of back end operations, require heavy dose of technology, which over the years has been developed and perfected by foreign players.

Challenges for Global Retailers in Indian Retail Sector

History has witnessed that the concern of allowing unrestrained FDI flows in the retail sector has never been free from controversies and simultaneously has been an issue for unsuccessful deliberation ever since the advent of FDI in India. Where on one hand there has been a strong outcry for the unrestricted flow of FDI in the retail trading by an overwhelming number of both domestic as well as foreign corporate retail giants; to the contrary, the critics of unrestrained FDI have always fiercely retorted by highlighting the adverse impact, the FDI in the retail trading will have on the unorganized retail trade, which is the source of employment to an enormous amount of the population of India. The antagonists of FDI in retail sector oppose the same on various grounds, like, that the entry of large global retailers such as Wal-Mart would kill local shops and millions of jobs, since the unorganized retail sector employs an enormous percentage of Indian population after the agriculture sector; secondly that the global retailers would conspire and exercise monopolistic power to raise prices and monopolistic (big buying) power to reduce the prices received by the suppliers; thirdly, it would lead to asymmetrical growth in cities, causing IJMMR Volume 1, Issue 1 (December, 2010) ISSN-2229-6883 Sri Krishna International Research & Educational Consorhttp://www.skirec.com tium - 62 - discontent and social tension elsewhere. Hence, both the consumers and the suppliers would lose, while the profit margins of such retail chains would go up. Many trading associations, political parties and industrial associations have argued against FDI in retailing due to various reasons. It is generally argued that the Indian retailers have yet to consolidate their position. The existing retailing scenario is characterized by the presence of a large number of fragmented family owned businesses, who would

not be able to survive the competition from global players. The examples of south east Asian countries show that after allowing FDI, the domestic retailers were marginalised and this led to unemployment. Another apprehension is that FDI in retailing can upset the import balance, as large international retailers may prefer to source majority of their products globally rather than investing in local products. The global retailers might resort to predatory pricing. Due to their financial clout, they often sell below cost in the new markets. Once the domestic players are wiped out of the market foreign players enjoy a monopoly position which allows them to increase prices and earn profits. Indian retailers have argued that since lending rates are much higher in India, Indian retailers, especially small retailers, are at a disadvantageous position compared to foreign retailers who have access to International funds at lower interest rates. High cost of borrowing forces the domestic players to charge higher prices for the products. Another argument against FDI is that FDI in retail trade would not attract large inflows of foreign investment since very little investment is required to conduct retail business. Goods are bought on credit and sales are made on cash basis. Hence, the working capital requirement is negligible. On the contrary; after making initial investment on basic infrastructure, the multinational retailers may remit the higher amount of profits earned in India to their own country.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Amidst today's time of fierce competition and a quest to achieve and enhance a substantial level of economic and social development; each and every nation is trying to liberalize its economic policies in order to attract investments from not only, domestic players, but also from magnates all across the globe. Consequently, people with generous reserves of funds, all around the globe, are expanding their wings and seeking opportunities of investing in different spheres of this lucrative market. India too is not oblivious to the rapid developments taking place in the global market and has emerged as one of the prime destinations for the investment of funds from an impressive number of foreign investors. In recent times the consumer are showing much greater confidence and in a due response the retail players in the market are veering towards aggressive expansion plan. These developments are clearly signaling an affluent time for retail sector. As the organised retail space in India continues to grow, it is likely to see a number of initiatives in the near future. Companies are likely to combine expansion with innovative measures as they look to ensure profitability in difficult times. Players need to increase their investments in retail ancillaries and retail logistics to ensure sustained benefits. As a survival strategy, moves are on to

allow FDI in the multi-brand retailing sector and there is fresh flow of equity investment in this sector which will definitely give the Indian retail sector a much needed boost. The advantages of allowing unrestrained FDI in the retail sector evidently outweigh the disadvantages attached to it and the same can be deduced from the examples of successful experiments in countries like Thailand and China; where too the issue of allowing FDI in the retail sector was first met with incessant protests, but later turned out to be one of the most promising political and economical decisions of their governments and led not only to the commendable rise in the level of employment but also led to the enormous development of their country's GDP. Besides, it would also lead to inflow of latest technical knowhow, establishment of well integrated and sophisticated supply chains, availability of standard, latest and quality products help in up gradation of human skills and increased sourcing from India.

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